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WP2: System Requirements

D2.1 Specification of Scientific Requirements Report

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Abstract

Sedimentary environments, volcanic environments, metamorphic and plutonic environments are the most common geological setting found on Earth. The FlyRadar instrument will have to be able to explore sedimentary objects, lava flow fields and metamorphic domains to produce geolocalised radargrams. These radargrams will be studied to define the major discontinuities in the underground to depth of about 10 to 20 m, to estimate the nature of these discontinuities, to measure the thickness or volume of the layers and give indication to their formation. The expected vertical resolution that is the minimum distance between two discontinuities that will be visible on the radargram should be at least of 0.1 m. The horizontal resolution should be also at least of 0.1 m. On the Earth, the nature of rock will be easily determined from field inspection, however the FlyRadar instrument will be used mostly to determine the geometry of the underground completed with such information on context. As radar signals are strongly affected by the presence of liquid water in the subsurface (that is very common on Earth), the FlyRadar instrument will be used mostly in dry areas that are arid hot deserts, karsts or cold arid areas where water is frozen.

On Mars the main geological environments are the same than on the Earth, thus the same expectations are required on Mars and on Earth. On Mars, the nature of rocks is sometimes difficult to define from only inspection on satellite images and multispectral or hyperspectral images. So, the FlyRadar instrument will be used also to estimate in some possible cases, the permittivity of the investigated underground to get values of porosity and density of the investigated rocks. These data will help to classify the geological environment and the rock nature. Moreover, very high resolution images (HiRISE, CTX) and spectra (CRISM) of the Martian surface are available or can be obtain on request. These imaging datasets will be a base to define the possible size and geometry of the objects which analogues the Earth will be investigated by the FlyRadar instrument. As the presence of liquid water is certainly very rare in the first meters of the Martian crust, the FlyRadar instrument will be able to operate over most of the Martian surface expected in areas dominated by clays.

The data of the FlyRadar instrument will depend on the frequency at which the instrument operates. At high frequencies, the vertical resolution will be optimum but the penetration of the signal will be low in the underground. At low frequencies, the vertical resolution will get worse but the signal will reach a greater depth. So a tradeoff has to be defined according to the geology of the investigated areas. The FlyRadar instrument should have the possibility to operate in a large band of frequencies. For a given experiment, the frequency will be defined in interaction between the scientific and the engineering team.

1.Introduction

This deliverable is the first of the WP 2 which aims is to define the requirements necessary to start the UAV and the onboard radar definition and construction. In this deliverable we describe the use of UAV for terrestrial scientific exploration of the surface and Earth interior, and also for planetary exploration. Then we describe scientific and user requirements for both Earth and Mars.

UAV's can be defined as an Unmanned Autonomous Flying Vehicle. Professional UAV (also called drone) are equipped by positioning and attitude sensors that ensure the flight and by scientific sensors to record the data from the target. Since about ten years, the use of UAV's for environmental studies has strongly increased because progresses in electronics permitted a miniaturization of sensors. UAV's, mainly equipped with electric engines, have become very flexible and secure also. The flight autonomy has also been increased and can reach now 30 minutes with a payload of about 4 kg. Now, missions with UAV's are planned and are effective to study other bodies of the solar systems. Now in 2021, Ingenuity is flying over the surface of Mars to demonstrate the efficiency of this technology, and the UAV DragonFly will fly over the surface of Titan in 2034.

The development of radar technology started in the 50' (see Deliverable 1.1 of the FlyRadar project). Radar for solid -Earth Sciences was used in two ways. SAR (Synthetic aperture radars) were installed on board of planes and satellite to obtain images of the Earth surface whatever the meteorological conditions were. These data are processed to obtain surface parameters such as surface roughness, or surface material properties. Pairs or temporal series of data can be processed by interferometric technics to identify surface changes or measure surface displacements. Radar is also used for the estimation of penetrative properties of electromagnetic waves. In dry condition, electromagnetic waves can cross the surface, can penetrate the ground and can be reflected on lithological interfaces. This property is used to obtain images of the underground (see deliverable 1.1).

2. Terrestrial exploration with a Low Frequency Radar carried by a drone

2.1 State of the Art

2.1.1 Development of UAV's for civil use

UAV's are autonomous flying platforms equipped with positioning and attitude sensors for piloting and guidance (e.g. Zang et al., 2019) as well as sensors able to measure a wide variety of environmental parameters. These aircrafts use autopilots which allow them to follow a path previously programmed on the ground before take-off. Onboard data logging systems store flight information and information acquired by environmental sensors. In some cases, for situations requiring real time, the information is sent by Wi-Fi or radio communication to the ground for processing or interpretation. The use of UAVs is now common, whether for research, surveillance or data acquisition for land use planning, etc. The rise and democratization of UAVs dates back to around 20 years ago when commercial autopilots were freely available. The first UAVs were equipped with heat engines. Gradually, in the 2010s, heat engines were replaced by electric motors. The geometry of the aircraft has evolved from flying wings or classic helicopters to multicopters providing more stability and safety in flight. Along with technical developments, regulatory developments have emerged to ensure the safety of people and goods. The first regulations were national. The implementation of European regulations homogenizing flight conditions across the EU will be in place in 2022.

The rise of UAVs also corresponds to a phase of miniaturization of electronics ensuring a reduction of the weight of the sensors. For example, a digital camera on board a UAV in the early 2000s could weigh 1 kg for a resolution under 1 M pixels. Currently, sensors with a resolution better than 20 M pixels are common and weigh less than 0.1 kg.

Along with the miniaturization of sensors, considerable progress has been made in battery technologies, essential accessories for today's UAV's. Batteries from the 2010s could provide flights of up to 10 minutes for on-payloads of less than one kg. Now the autonomy of electric UAV's has increased considerably and can reach up to 50 minutes with a payload of 4 to 5 kg.

The environmental sensors that UAV's can be equipped with are very diverse. Image sensors are the most conventionally used, whether they are classical cameras, video cameras or even sensitive multi or hyperspectral sensors in the visible, near infrared or thermal infrared, spectrum. There are also sensors for measuring the intensity and direction of the magnetic or electric field. Recently, gas analyzers light enough to be carried on board a UAV have been developed. There are also sensors for measuring radioactivity as well as directional sound sensors working from the infra-sounds to the ultra-sounds. Lidars are now conventionally on board UAV's to measure topographies.

All data acquired by the sensors described above must be geolocated before being processed. It is therefore essential that the positioning and attitude information recorded during the flight be perfectly synchronized with the clock of the environmental sensors. This protocol is delicate but essential. Its precision ensures the reliability of data spatialization.

Currently there is only one supplier of UAVs equipped with SAR radar (Fasano et al., 2017). This is the American company Imsar associated with the company Unmanned System Technology, manufacturer of UAVs (<https://www.unmannedsystemstechnology.com/company/imsar/>) which builds UAVs equipped with SAR for imaging territory and the tracking of moving targets. There is no off-the-shelf product that produces surface (SAR) and subsurface (GPR) images (see deliverable 1.1).

2.1.2 UAV's Data for scientific exploration of the Earth

As written above, UAV's can be equipped with a variety of sensors that have made it possible to acquire data in many scientific disciplines related to Earth sciences, biology, glaciology or oceanography.

UAV's were used very early on to acquire stereoscopic images that could be processed by photogrammetry techniques to obtain Digital Elevation Models (matrix of data in which each box contains an altitude value at a given position) and orthoimages (plane images projected in a cartographic or geographical reference system). From these data, it is possible to precisely define the size and shape of the objects as well as their evolution over time if successive missions are carried out. These data are useful for sedimentology, tectonics, study of natural hazards, etc. Thermal infrared images have been used to monitor volcanoes and hydrothermal fields. These data are essential for carrying out a thermal balance on the scale of a volcanic

edifice (e.g. Fedele, et al., 2021). Gas sensors help to sample gas emitted in fumarole environment in a more safety way than conventional technics (e.g. Mochammad et al., 2016). The magnetic field and its anomalies are frequently measured (e.g. Gailler et al., 2021) to detect mineralization in the subsoil. Multispectral or hyperspectral data in the near infrared and mid-infrared domains are classically used for the production of mineralogical or geological maps (Jaud et al., 2016).

UAV's are also used for biology. Very high spatial resolution images make help to map plant species (Osco et al., 2020). It is also possible to determine the presence of warm-blooded animals from thermal images in areas covered by vegetation (e.g., Ward et al., 2016). Glaciology also uses UAV's to obtain information on the volumes and changes in volume of glaciers. It is also possible to determine the surface texture of ice. Oceanography uses data from UAV's for the survey of coastlines (Delacourt et al., 2009). It is possible to measure the characteristics of the waves from videos or the composition of the water column from hyperspectral data (Jaud et al., 2018).

2.1.3 Radars for scientific exploration of the Earth

Radars on board of satellite or aerial platforms for exploring the Earth were developed in the 1970s. The first satellite platform carrying radar was NASA's Seasat, which allowed observation of the oceans. The first mission to observe the continents was the ESA ERS-1 mission followed by the RadarSatt (Canadian Space Agency) then Sentinel (ESA) and CosmoSkymed (ASI) (Fagioli et al., 2006) missions. These ongoing platforms allow high resolution spatial and temporal monitoring of the Earth's surface. These radar data can be processed to map areas under cloud cover and to map changes in surface conditions or to measure movements (InSar techniques – Aslan et al., 2019).

Ground Penetrating Radar has never been spatialized or even on board an airplane. The GPR is inoperative in the presence of liquid water and therefore in the presence of plant cover or in the presence of high clay content. GPRs are therefore used from the ground for geotechnical applications (research of electric or water networks), archaeology (research of buried constructions - Orlando, 2013), glaciology (measurement of ice thickness – Fisher, 2009) or geology (detection and measurement of the geometry of sedimentary bodies in desert conditions – Lejzerowicz, 2014).

As written above, there is only one commercial solution of a UAV equipped with SAR radar. There is no commercial solution for a GPR (Ground Penetrating Radar - see deliverable 1) on board a UAV. Thus this project is pioneering in this aspect.

2.2 User requirements

The system to be developed in this project should provide radargram (radargram is a graphic representation of the measurement of a radar penetrating ground or materials) ready to interpret. It generally represents on the abscissa a length corresponding to the distance of the line analyzed, on the ordinate a time corresponding to the response time of the signal between its emission and its reception, and a color gradient corresponding to the amplitude of the

signal. This diagram makes it possible to visualize the geometrical characteristics of a subsurface ground unit, or of a material, and to represent the shapes as well as the internal details.) The geographic localization needs to be accurate enough to link the data to already existing maps and surface outcrops.

2.3 Scientific requirements

As scientific requirements we describe those critical aspects, which the data provided by the radar should fulfill, in order to gain scientifically relevant results. However, there is a wide range of various expected parameters of the targets, thus these requirements are mainly generalized, but useful for orientation. The description below gives an overview of the possible geological environments that could be explored by a drone equipped with a radar with possible sets of geometrical parameters. A radar will produce useful data only if the electromagnetic waves that it delivers toward the ground are, at least partly, reflected by an interface and not completely absorbed by the ground (see D1.1). Electromagnetic waves in the range of 100 MHz to 1 GHz are absorbed by liquid water, by metals or other conductive medias, and by clays. In presence of ice, radar can be operative if no liquid water is associated to that ice. On the Earth that corresponds to subsurface temperature below -20°C .

2.3.1 Sedimentary environments Sedimentary environments are widespread on Earth. Sedimentary rocks, generally deposited in layer bounded by sharp discontinuities, present a strong interest to be explored by a GPR (e.g. Lang et al., 2017). This method is complementary with field investigations to define geometry from surface outcrops that is thickness of layers, dip and dip direction of layers, 3D layer organization and stacking patterns. 3D reconstructions of layer geometry help to understand the facies architecture (Carling et al., 2016), while field investigations provide compositional and porosity data. For example (Fig. 1) GPR is classically used to investigate fan delta deposits in continental environments (Land et al., 2017). This example represents the most complex sedimentary structure that can be observed on Earth: discontinuous and short layers with a strong dip, lenticular deposits, erosion surfaces, low permittivity contrast between layers. This structure is investigated to a depth of 5 meters on more than 50 m long.

Figure 1: Example of GPR section and interpretation of a distal gravel-rich subaqueous ice-contact fan deposits- Porta fan and delta complex (Germany). The system was active during Middle Pleistocene. The frequency of the GPR was set on 400MHz (Lang et al., 2017).

Rock porosity can also be indirectly estimated from GPR measurement. For a given lithology, rock permittivity varies according to the amount of void. The CRIM methods (complex refractive index model – Conti et al.) is used to estimate the possible porosity of the subsurface from GPR and the amount of water in the porosity. This technique requires the registration of the full wave reflection of the electromagnetic signal that is seldom available from commercial GPR.

2.3.2 Volcanic environments

Volcanic environments are common on Earth. It is important to investigate geometry of volcanic layers both for science and for risk mitigation. Volcanic layers can be defined by their thickness, their dip and dip orientation, and by the internal organization of layers which testify to the volcanic dynamics and its evolution over time. Figure 2 (Gomez et al., 2018), shows a radargram obtained on a recent volcanic series from the Semeru volcano in Indonesia. Volcanic layers are clearly visible despite they are discontinuous and heterogeneous. The depth of investigation is around 10 m and the thickness of the volcanic layers is one meter or less.

Figure 2: Example of a GRP (500 MHz) section in volcanic environment (Semeru volcano, Indonesia) (Gomez et al., 2018). From such section, it is possible to estimate the thickness of the volcanic layers and to propose or to confirm the history of the volcanic deposits, to measure the thickness and volumes of the various volcanic deposits, and to determine size and position of the larger clasts (red dots) included in the volcanic layers. Notice that the vertical axis of the upper image is in time, that is the geometry is distorted and need to be corrected. That is done in the lower image.

GPR are also able to determine the position depth, orientation and thickness of dikes. Dikes, which may not be visible on the surface, are an expression of volcanism that is necessary to characterize (Gomez-Ortiz et al., 2006). In the example of Fig. 3, the volcanic deposits appear strongly layered while the vertical dike intruding the lava deposit is transparent. On Earth the width of dikes ranges from few centimetres to 100 m. The thinnest are probably difficult to detect but those with a width of more than 0.5 m that are the most common and

significant in terms of geodynamics and volcanic dynamics fall in the range of detectable objects.

Figure 3: Radargram (top) and interpretation of the lava flow of the Pico Veijo (Tenerife Island - Spain). (A) lava flow, (B) intruding dike (Gomez-Ortiz et al., 2006). The frequency of the GPR was set on 100Mhz.

Richardson & Karlstrom (2019) showed using modelling technics of lava flow emplacement on complex topographies and spectral decomposition of these topographies that most of the lava flows on earth have a thickness that ranges from 1 to 10 m. The thickness depends by a power law of the length of the flow.

2.3.3 Metamorphic and plutonic domains

Metamorphic areas are generally complex and difficult to characterize from GRP data. Indeed, they are affected by numerous discontinuities such as foliation, fractures, faults etc. and can present a complex internal geometry with different families of folds of different orientation and geometry. That is why GRP is seldom used in such terrains. However, in particular cases for which no information is available from surface (no outcrop such as on

weathered and flat areas), GPR data can help to define the different families of fractures by their orientation (Silva et al., 2004).

Figure 4: Radargram (top) and interpretation (bottom) in the crystalline area of Caicara Farm (Brazil, Silva et al., 2004). The discontinuities visible in the radargram are interpreted as fractures or faults. Most of the reflectors are interpreted as being of the metamorphic foliation. The frequency of the GPR was set on 80MHz.

2.3.4 Geometry and resolution expected from the FlyRadar instrument for Earth investigation

The geometry and resolution that is needed for the FlyRadar instrument for Earth investigation is defined in Table 1. From the information mentioned in the previous paragraphs, it appears that the expectations are similar in the various geological environments.

Table 1: Expectations of the FlyRadar instrument in terms of vertical and horizontal resolution, depths of investigation according to various geological environments, based on analogue tests on the Earth.

Environment	Geometry related parameters	Resolution
Sedimentary environment	<p>Able to distinguish layers with thicknesses ranging from 0.1 to 1 m</p> <p>Able to measure dip ranging from 0 to 45°</p> <p>Able to estimate indirectly rock porosity</p>	<p>Vertical resolution from 0.1 to 1 m</p> <p>Horizontal resolution of 0.1 m</p> <p>Depth of investigation : 10 m</p>
Volcanic environments	<p>Able to distinguish layers with thicknesses ranging from 0.1 to 10 m</p> <p>Able to detect sharp variations</p> <p>Able to measure dip from 0 to 90°</p>	<p>Vertical resolution from 0.1 to 10m</p> <p>Horizontal resolution of 0.1m</p> <p>Depth of investigation 10m</p>
Metamorphic environments	<p>The system has to be sensitive to foliation, fractures and faults</p>	<p>Vertical resolution better than 0.1 m</p> <p>Horizontal resolution better than 0.1</p> <p>Depths investigation up to 10m</p>

3. Planetary exploration with a low frequency radar carried by a drone

3.1 State of the Art

Only one drone has been flown beyond the Earth till 2021, the Ingenuity by NASA on Mars, and there is another already accepted mission under development called DragonFly for Titan. These projects as examples are described below.

Ingenuity (Mars 2020 – mission in progress, NASA)

Autonomous electric copter associated to the Perseverance rover, as demonstrator with no scientific objective. Demonstration instrument with 2 cameras one PAN and one colour, able to recharge itself from solar panel, fly few minutes in a quiet atmosphere in order to prove powered flight in the thin atmosphere of Mars. The Red Planet has lower gravity (about one-third that of Earth) but its atmosphere is just 1% as thick, making it much harder to generate lift. The detailed aims are:

- Demonstrate miniaturized flying technology that requires shrinking down onboard computers, electronics and other parts so that the helicopter is light enough to take off.
- Operate autonomously. Ingenuity will use solar power to charge its batteries and rely on internal heaters to maintain operational temperatures during the cold Martian nights. After receiving commands from Earth relayed through the rover, each test flight is performed without real-time input from Mars Helicopter mission controllers.

DragonFly (arrival planned for 2034, NASA)

DragonFly is an autonomous drone with 8-bladed rotorcraft designed to fly in the thick atmosphere of Titan which is Saturn's largest and richly organic moon. Using vertical take-off and landing technology, DragonFly will visit and sample several locations, flying up to 4 km above the surface and travel with up to 10 m/s speed and take up to 8 km distance per flight, using radioactive energy source providing 70 W. The 450 kg probe will be active only daytime and stay on the surface during the 8 Earth day long night-time. The payload of the probe will contain the following instruments:

- DraMS (Dragonfly Mass Spectrometer) is a mass spectrometer to identify chemical components, especially those relevant to biological processes, in surface and atmospheric samples.
- DraGNS (Dragonfly Gamma-Ray and Neutron Spectrometer), consists of a deuterium-tritium Pulsed Neutron Generator and a set of a gamma-ray spectrometer and neutron spectrometer to identify the surface composition under the lander.
- DraGMet (Dragonfly Geophysics and Meteorology Package) is a suite of meteorological sensors including a seismometer.
- DragonCam (Dragonfly Camera Suite) is a set of microscopic and panoramic cameras to image Titan's terrain and scout for scientifically interesting landing sites.

3.2 Scientific requirements for Martian exploration

As demonstrated in the Deliverable 1.1, the geology of Mars is rich and complex. Sedimentary, volcanic, glacial and erosional processes have shaped the surface from millimeter to kilometer scales. Volcanic and sedimentary deposits and icy layers are common and classically observed on high resolution images provided by spatial probes or by rovers.

The major question that a radar on board of a UAV can solve is the geometry of these structures at depths.

The use of GPR could support future missions with the following aspects: mainly to obtain information on the geometry at depth, to obtain information on surface micro-roughness (impossible to obtain from classical photometric technics), provide information on geotechnical properties of the regolith, on ISRU (in-situ resource utilization) possibilities in general, especially provide information on ice occurrence and scientific targeting. Safety aspects might be also considered using radar properties at specific terrains related to stability where subsurface voids exist or extensive drilling and excavation is planned.

On Mars beside the classical ice caps various icy **targets should be considered**, among them mainly middle and high latitude buried or rarely outcropping ice masses, however loose snow-like layers are also expected in the top meter(s) of the regolith in this region. Considering such icy terrains, the geometry of the basement, possibly the geometry of internal layers of ice with various dust content could be targeted with decametric resolution to 10 m depth.

To resolve various subsurface features, it is worth considering the scale of the **expected targets**. Based on the surface and orbital datasets of Mars, the following scales of target features might occur and possible to identify by a shallow subsurface radar.

3.2.1 Example targets based on **SHARAD radar data**

Surveying SHARAD profiles of potential targets, the Figure 5 gives some examples of Martian surface structures that could be studied with a GRP on-board of a UAV. In the figure pairs of panels show the THEMIS (Mars Odyssey Mission – Thermal and Panchromatic images) based optical appearance (left) of these example terrains with the corresponding radar profile, while the radargram along this given profile can be seen next to it (right) with dark background. The yellow text marks the name or type and some characteristics of the candidate target features.

Figure 5: Examples of various SHARAD based subsurface features in the top 200-400 m thick subsurface units. Although this range is larger than what the FlyRADAR based GPR aims, still useful to demonstrate the possibilities and main problems of defining subsurface features. The radargrams can be seen with dark background, while the terrains optical appearance can be seen in the grey panes. Specific details of the profiles can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Details of the targets presented in figure 5.

type	specific location	SHARAD profile	characteristics
a) mass moved debris	20.60N 303.09E	S_0258560 3	possible buried subsurface location is visible as reflector
b) Interior Layered Deposits	11.15S 286.22E	S_0347450 1	probable buried layers inside sediments in Valles Marineris with strong subsurface reflectors
e) LVF a the edge of Arabia Terra no1		S_0664810 1	sublayers below the short section of LVF
c) chaotic blocks from mass movement	6.99S 274.53E	S_0464950 1	great wall slump produced debris field in Valles Marineris, forming weak radar reflection area
e) LVF forms near Arabia Terra no2		S_0652350 2	subductions and glacial movement forms
f) possible sedimentary fan			A possible sedimentary fan at the Apollinaris Patera, although poorly visible

3.2.2. Example targets based on **HiRISE images**

Surveying about 100 HiRISE images acquired of such surface feature types, which have been discussed as potential targets in the D1.1 document, the following examples show the existence of subsurface structures expected to be observable in the top 10-20 m with radar to be developed. In table 3 some examples are listed for the observed structures in the shallow subsurface, exposed by erosion and/or at slopes. These features are usually too small to be resolved by SHARAD, however could be widespread on Mars, and their indications can be found often as exposed layer heads could be identified in HiRISE images (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Surface exposed shallow subsurface structures on HiRISE images. Lines correspond to lines (and panel no.) in the Table 3. First column shows 100 km diameter terrain using THEMIS images for context, second column shows about 4 km diameter part of the HiRISE images, while third column shows 1x1 km magnified section of the images.

Table 3: Parameters of the HiRISE images indicated in Figure 6

type	HiRISE image no.	coordinates	characteristics	panel no,
crater filling lava or sediments	ESP_069 970_174 5	5.45S 67.53E	roughly 1 Ga aged crater filling material (lava or sediment) with exposed subsurface layering by a smaller impact crater along an about 380 m high slope, probably of sedimentary or lava flow layering origin	a
mantling layer	ESP_069 969_219 0	38.53N 88.61E	recent, some Ma old dust+ice deposition with climatic signatures, layer thickness based on shadow length around 6-12 m	b
scalloped terrains	ESP_069 956_224 0	43.74N 83.20E	Utopia Planitia cryokarstic terrains, eroded recently deposited volatiles layers of about 2-4 m deep	c
subsurface voids	ESP_069 948_207 5	27.44N 302.85 E	collapsed subsurface voids, which might emerge as lack of radar echoes, however in theory at many locations might be ice filled on Mars	d
layered deposits on valley floor	ESP_069 947_152 0	27.95S 337.84 E	section of a fluvial valley with 20-25 m thin surface layer cover, possibly formed as earlier fluvial activity or more probable younger sedimentary unit	e
layering in Western Arabia Terra	ESP_069 933_190 0	9.69N 355.34 E	erosion exposed shallow subsurface layering in Western Arabia Terra, several quasi-parallel layers are present with about meter thickness	f
dune covered terrains	ESP_069 896_173 5	6.54S 287.46 E	bottom level of Candor Chasma probably covered by ancient sediments, but recently became covered by dunes with 1-10 m thickness, with some exposed locations	g

Based on the items listed in Tables 2 and 3 the following expectations are relevant for shallow radar survey on Mars: there are abundant layering, mainly from recently deposited

ice-dust sediments, however there are older structures also. Dunes and dust cover at many locations are present at the surface, however these do not provide strong reflection based on SHARAD observations. If the some m thick / deep layers in the subsurface could be linked to surface exposures and stratigraphic levels, they could provide a good possibility for reconstruction of the geological history. This level / depth also important for future manned mission and local ISRU activity there.

Table 4: Science Traceability Matrix for FlyRadar analogue work. Comments: A: Relative velocity in two different media could we estimated by calculating the Brewster angle (Reppert P.M., Morgan F.D., Toksoz M.N. 2000. Dielectric constant determination using ground-penetrating radar reflection coefficients. *Journal of Applied Geophysics* 43, 189–197. B: Measuring for the surface the Intensity of radar reflection of SHARAD decreases downward probably as regolith is more fragmented closer to the surface.

Goal	Science objective	Parameters to be determined	Uncertainties
identify subsurface target properties	separate different subsurface units related to compositional or structural changes	<p>identify interfaces between different subsurface units</p> <p>quantify the relative dielectric constant ratio at interface boundaries where the radar wave is travelling between changing velocity medium (A)</p> <p>identify supporting compositional information from orbital spectroscopy (Mars), and from in-situ data (analogs on Earth)</p>	<p>beside mineralogy dielectric constant is influenced by porosity, pore fluids, geometry what should be estimated or measured as ground truth</p> <p>surface composition is not necessarily representative for the subsurface</p>
	identify micro-scale structural properties	porosity, characteristics of fragmentation level	target geometry and pore filling material dependent
	estimate surface weathering related aspects	intensity change of radar reflection downward on Mars in the regolith (B), similar does not necessarily emerge on the Earth, possibly except old rocks terrain	poorly known, other parameters might also influence the increased reflectance toward the surface
identify formation	constrain formation	horizontal and vertical change of radar based	difficulty to identify the same formation

processes of the target	methods using subsurface locations and target properties	properties to identify spatial and temporal changes of the target features	and lithological units at not direct neighborhood
	link subsurface features' properties, location and context to optically observed surface structures, indicative of formation methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -identify surface outcrops' subsurface continuation -identify geographic location of the given radar defined subsurface features -estimate "paleo-surface" context: was a given unit at an elevated site or inside a depression previously 	surface outcrops are rare and targets are often covered by fresh debris
identify geological history of the target	identify stratigraphic relation and environmental changes	depth / distances of different reflectors, evaluation of sequence of identified layers, layer deformation, horizontal continuity / discontinuity	usually only few different chronostratigraphic units could be separated

Based on the Table 4 it is unavoidable that **supplementary information** beside the recorded radar data is necessary for interpretation and improvement of the scientific results. This required information is:

- compositional data: could be acquired from spectral data (THEMIS, OMEGA, CRISM) for Mars and field sampling and later laboratory analysis of target rocks at analogues sites on the Earth
- structural information especially on porosity (although estimation from context and experience on reference target by radar is also possible)
- repeatability should be tested for reference targets at the first field tests
- in ideal case spatial resolution and radar reflection intensity should be also tested at reference targets (explored by outcrops)

Expected basic characteristics of subsurface units to estimate their observability (all data are for Mars, except the last column). During the compilation of the table, SHARAD based observability of Martian features received preferences, as they provide real examples – however FlyRadar project based observations might have increased spatial (both horizontal and vertical) resolution and decreased vertical penetration than SHARAD:

In rocks and sediments, dielectric properties are primarily a function of mineralogy, porosity, water saturation, frequency, and depending on the rock lithology, component geometries, and electrochemical interactions (Knight and Endres, 1990; Knoll, 1996). For a summary the requirements see Table 5.

Table 5: Requirement parameters to provide an overview of the scientific aims based requirement for the engineering constrains.

Parameter	Minimal / requirement	Ideal
record material quality related reflection intensity on Mars, and compositional differences by in-situ analysis	separate porous and competent rocks, separate bedrock from fragmented/weathered regolith	differentiate between basalt, sulfate, identify
geographical position of the measurements	resolution to embed and locate the acquired results in already existing geological maps for context	as high resolution as the existing reference datasets (maps, images)
horizontal spatial resolution	1 m	0.1 m
vertical spatial resolution (time delay measurement for different subsurface reflectors)	0.5 m	0.1 m

The storing of produced data rate should be enough to fulfil all the minimal / required constrains together with spatial information, recorded date and housekeeping data.

4. Conclusions

Sedimentary environments, volcanic environments, metamorphic and plutonic environments are the most common geological setting found on Earth. The FlyRadar instrument will have to be able to explore sedimentary objects, lava flow fields and metamorphic domains to produce geolocalised radargrams. These radargrams will be studied to define the major discontinuities in the underground to depth of 10 to 20 m, to estimate the nature of these discontinuities and to measure the thickness or volume of the layers. The expected vertical resolution that is the minimum distance between two discontinuities what will be visible on the radargram should be at least of 0.1 m. The horizontal resolution should be also at least of 0.1 m. On the Earth, the nature of rock will be easily determined from field inspection. The FlyRadar instrument will be used mostly to determine the geometry of the underground. As radar signal are strongly affected by the presence of liquid water that is very common of

Earth, the FlyRadar instrument will be used mostly in dry areas that are arid hot deserts, karsts or cold arid areas where water is frozen.

On Mars the main geological environments are the same than on the Earth, however heavily metamorphosed targets are not expected – so the same expectations are required on Mars and on Earth. On Mars, the nature of rocks is sometimes difficult to define from only inspection on satellite images and spectra. Thus the FlyRadar instrument will be used also to determine, in some possible cases, the permittivity of the investigated underground units to get values of porosity and density of the target rocks. These data will help to classify the geological environment and the rock nature. Moreover, very high resolution images of the Martian surface are available or can be obtained on request. These images will be a base to define the possible size and geometry of the analogue object on the Earth investigated by the FlyRadar instrument. As the presence of liquid water is certainly very rare in the first meters of the Martian crust, the FlyRadar instrument will be able to operate over most of the Martian surface excepted in areas dominated by clays.

Some characteristics of the data of the FlyRadar instrument will depend on the frequency at which the instrument operates. At high frequencies, the vertical resolution will be optimum but the penetration of the signal will be low in the underground. At low frequencies, the vertical resolution will be worse but the signal will reach a greater depth. So a trade off has to be defined according to the geology of the investigated areas. The FlyRadar instrument should have the possibility to operate in a large band of frequencies. For a given experiment, the frequency will be defined in interaction between the scientific and the engineering team.

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END OF REPORT

